

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF AQUATIC DISEASE

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Resume. A comparative analysis of the incidence and clinical course of chickenpox in 290 patients admitted to the infectious disease hospital of the Bukhara region in 2022-2023 is presented. It was found that children between the ages of 3 and 14 years were hospitalized significantly more often, and among adults - between the ages of 18 and 34 years (1,3-7). Symptoms of chickenpox in the nervous system did not differ significantly between adults and children. Rashes in children are characterized by the localization of the body on the trunk and extremities, and in adults - on the face and trunk (2). Children have a lower intensity of itching than adults, and enanthema on the mucous membranes is less common. Lymphadenopathy in children has a general character, but is less pronounced than in patients over 18 years of age. The duration of the intoxication syndrome and the length of hospitalization were not significantly different in children and adults (4). The obtained data can be used to predict the course and consequences of chickenpox in children and adult patients.

Key words: chicken pox, children, adults, clinical presentation, complications

Among airborne infections (except influenza and acute respiratory viral infection), the share of chickenpox is 60-70%. It is determined by the high level of the disease, its ubiquitous distribution, the increase in the share of the total infectious pathology, significant economic damage and the ineffectiveness of non-specific preventive measures implemented in practice. Chickenpox (Varisella) is an acute infectious anthroponotic disease caused by a virus belonging to the Herpesviridae family, transmitted by airborne droplets, with fever, moderate intoxication, widespread vesicular rash.

Materials and methods. This article presents the results of 2-year monitoring of chickenpox in 290 patients treated in the regional clinical center.

According to the results and discussion, in 2022–2023. 290 patients aged 8 months to 58 years were hospitalized and treated with a diagnosis of chickenpox. Childhood patients made up 69.4% (201 people), over 18 years old - 30.6% (89 people). When analyzing the age structure of treated children, it was noted that more children aged 3 to 7 (106 people - 52.7%) were admitted to the

hospital; From 8 months to 3 years - 58 people, 29%, from 7 to 14 years - 37 people, 18.3%, boys were sick more often (54.4%). Among adults, mainly men aged 18-34 were admitted to the hospital.

Summary. Among the patients admitted to the hospital with a confirmed diagnosis of "chickenpox", children aged 3 to 14 years dominated significantly.

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